

SCRIPTED ROLE-PLAYS TO SUPPORT EFL LEARNERS ABILITY TO PRODUCE CONNECTED SPEECH WHEN READING ALOUD

JUEGOS DE ROL GUIONIZADOS PARA APOYAR LA CAPACIDAD DE LOS ESTUDIANTES DE INGLÉS COMO LENGUA EXTRANJERA EN PRODUCIR UN DISCURSO CONECTADO AL LEER EN VOZ ALTA

INTERPRETAÇÃO DE PAPÉIS COM ROTEIRO PARA APOIAR A CAPACIDADE DOS ALUNOS DE INGLÊS DE PRODUZIR DISCURSO CONECTADO POR MEIO DA LEITURA EM VOZ ALTA

ABSTRACT

This action research study describes a five-session intervention aimed to explore the use of scripted role-play as a strategy to support the ability to produce connected speech in English in 9th graders from a private school in Chile. The success of the intervention was measured by using quantitative and qualitative data to describe students' progress towards the use of role-plays to support their oral production of linking words and weak forms. Through a descriptive analysis, the quantitative data was analysed to measure improvement in participants' oral production. These data were triangulated with a focus group to identify students' perceptions of said support. The interventions showed to be significant as participants achieved improvement on their speaking skills from a 38% to a 76% respectively as well as reading aloud in English. The result revealed the strategy was effective in terms of producing linking words and weak forms by reading scripted role-plays aloud.

KEYWORDS: scripted role-play, speaking skills, reading aloud, connected speech.

RESUMEN

Este estudio de investigación-acción describe una intervención de cinco sesiones cuyo objetivo fue explorar el uso de juegos de rol guionizados como estrategia para apoyar la capacidad de producir un discurso conectado en inglés en estudiantes de 9.º grado de un colegio privado en Chile. El éxito de la intervención se midió utilizando datos cuantitativos y cualitativos para describir el progreso de los estudiantes en el uso de juegos de rol para apoyar su producción oral de palabras de enlace y formas

débiles. Mediante un análisis descriptivo, se analizaron los datos cuantitativos para medir la mejora en la producción oral de los participantes. Estos datos se triangularon con un grupo focal para identificar las percepciones de los estudiantes sobre dicho apoyo. Las intervenciones demostraron ser significativas, ya que los participantes lograron una mejora en sus habilidades de habla del 38% al 76%, respectivamente, así como en la lectura en voz alta en inglés. El resultado reveló que la estrategia fue efectiva en la producción de palabras de enlace y formas débiles mediante la lectura en voz alta de juegos de rol guionizados.

PALABRAS CLAVE: juego de rol guionizado, habilidades de expresión oral, lectura en voz alta, discurso continuo.

RESUMO

Este estudo de pesquisa-ação descreve uma intervenção de cinco sessões com o objetivo de explorar o uso de dramatizações roteirizadas como uma estratégia para apoiar a capacidade de produzir discurso conectado em inglês em alunos do 9º ano de uma escola particular no Chile. O sucesso da intervenção foi medido pelo uso de dados quantitativos e qualitativos para descrever o progresso dos alunos no uso de dramatizações para apoiar sua produção oral de palavras de ligação e formas fracas. Usando análise descritiva, os dados quantitativos foram analisados para medir a melhora na produção oral dos participantes. Esses dados foram triangulados com um grupo de foco para identificar as percepções dos alunos sobre esse apoio. As intervenções se mostraram significativas, com os participantes obtendo melhorias em suas habilidades de fala de 38% a 76%, respectivamente, bem como na leitura em voz alta em inglês. O resultado revelou que a estratégia foi eficaz em termos de produção de palavras de ligação e formas fracas por meio da leitura de drama em voz alta.

PALAVRAS-CHAVE: interpretação de papéis com roteiro, habilidades orais, leitura em voz alta, discurso conectado.

1 Introduction

The worldwide standard for categorising language proficiency is the Common European Framework of Reference for Languages (CEFR) across six distinct levels.

For instance, levels range from A1 for beginners to C2 for experts who have mastered the language (Council of Europe, 2001). In accordance with the A2 descriptor level of English, learners are able to easily communicate through a direct exchange of information on familiar, daily routines, and describe basic topics (Council of Europe, 2001). Taking this into consideration, the Chilean National Curriculum of Education (Ministerio de Educación de Chile, 2016) state learners in 9th grade should demonstrate content knowledge, coherence in the organization of ideas, and an appropriate use of language functions and sounds of the language in receptive skills (listening and reading), leaving aside the productive skills of speaking skills. In 9th graders' context, they are expected to communicate and read fluently as comprehensively as possible with minimum errors not leading distraction to the interlocutor's message. Nevertheless, the group of 9th graders certified in A2 Key (KET) present difficulties, errors with connected speech and utterance fluency (production of weak forms and linking words). Therefore, the teacher's role within this goal is monitoring and exposing students to the language in real-life situations as well as providing opportunities for them to practice spoken English.

In this action research study, it was aimed to explore the use of scripted role-plays as a strategy to support 9th grader's ability to produce connected speech in English to address the difficulties in the production of connected speech in 9th graders. The Communicative Language Teaching (CLT) approach was implemented since the role as a teacher under this strategy is being a facilitator rather than a straightforward instructor for communicative activities. According to Richards (2006) and Ortega-Auquilla et al. (2019) fluency is developed by creating classroom activities in which students negotiate meaning, use communication strategies, correct misunderstandings, and engage in meaningful interaction — maintaining intelligible and continuous communication despite the communicative constraints. This is highlighted in importance since such developing is not only linguistic competence but also involves pragmatic skills for authentic communication.

2 Theoretical Framework

Assessing reading aloud fluency.

The concept of fluency has been discussed from the perspective of productive skills, particularly in relation to spoken language. On one hand, the aspects of communication in influencing L2 fluency development are the link between cognition and utterance fluency, and these need to be positioned within the social context of communication (Segalowitz, 2010).

Richards, Platt, and Weber (1985, as cited in Brown, 2003) define the conceptualization of fluency as “the features which give speech the qualities of being natural and normal, including native-like use of pausing, rhythm, intonation, stress, rate of speaking, and use of interjections and interruptions” (p.1). Contrarily, Vargas (2018) states the concept of fluency is not only associated with using the language properly and in a natural rhythm but also involves pauses and interruptions that are typical in the mother tongue. Consequently, learners are taught to speak and use L2 by providing opportunities to practice and exposing them to the challenge of facing real-world situations (Vargas, 2018).

Furthermore, research studies suggest that comprehensive reading programs should be integrated on reading assessments that assess students' skills at the beginning, throughout, and at the end of a reading program due to the significance of assessing learners' oral reading fluency is to help teachers to determine the most effective fluency instruction to meet students' interests, needs, and abilities (Aldhanhani & Abu-Ayyash, 2020). The results of students' assessments allow teachers decide whether to develop, adapt, or integrate fluency strategies to engage students' interest and motivation for reading aloud. In addition, reading aloud' assessments could also provide teachers with information about the progress that students have and have not achieved. In the same vein, an analytical study conducted by Li and Doyle (2021) presents a theoretical discussion of the function of two core domains of reading fluency, the automatic word reading, the prosody, and the relations between them from a perspective of cognitive science.

Fluency in reading can be related to a cognitive fluency since reading requires the skills to recognize orthographic forms, connect them to their phonemic representations, and understand the meaning to decode the message. These skills can be measured by reading speed; increased fluency in this context indicates that the decoding and recognition of the units become faster (Nation, 2009). As a working

definition of fluency, “A fluent speech in a second or foreign language means been able to speak at length, with a minimum of unfilled pauses in non-juncture positions, incorporating features of connected speech, producing correct intonation and stress patterns, using formulaic language, and being able to interact with an interlocutor” (Cid Uribe & Cavallieri, 2018). As a conclusion from the action research about fostering fluency in EFL and ESL students through explicit instruction, it contributes to the acquisition of skills in higher levels of competence. For instance, preparing the first stage is to directly address the long-term benefits of strengthening speaking skills and inform learners the significance of being proficient in a language. Then, the role of a teacher plays onto the use of engaging teaching methods by drawing attention to the components of fluency that the teacher wishes to work on.

In language learning, these receptive skills, listening and reading, are opposite to the productive skills, speaking and writing (Council of Europe, 2001). All the four linguistic abilities rely on active cognitive processes which are distinct but also intertwined. In addition, these skills can be measured by reading speed; increased fluency in this context indicates that the decoding and recognition of the units becomes faster (Lintunen et al., 2019). On one hand, “*fluency*” is a perception on the part of the listener (Götz, 2013). Contrarily, Cid Uribe and Cavallieri (2018) state that fluency is a highly subjective concept. Therefore, drawing attention to the components of fluency teachers contemplate to include on their lessons by implementing authentic material could be a good way of approaching the fostering of fluency (Cid Uribe & Cavallieri, 2018).

Use of role-playing to support reading aloud skills.

A review of literature shows that several researchers have indicated the benefits of employing the role-playing technique among different contexts. Although the present study does not address the reading comprehension as a skill itself, it is important to point out the benefits of reading aloud (RA) technique. Rashtchi and Moradzadehb (2018) used the role-playing technique for storytelling classes, it was revealed that EFL learners had a more significant effect on the narrative writing than the reading a story aloud technique. However, the authors were able to conclude that the narrative writing was implicitly enhanced by engaging in the role-playing classes. Participants from their study were introduced concepts such as style, pattern, organization,

characters, relationships, and imaginative thinking from said technique and used them in their narrative writing. In the same vein, Abdoun and Melgani (2021) state that reading as a receptive skill competence is important as it is part of the four main English language functions to master in language teaching since there is a reciprocal relationship between the academic success and learner's academic reading skill. Their study aimed to research the effectiveness of using reading-aloud and thinking-aloud strategies on student's reading comprehension of EFL learners by following the competency-based approach. In addition, in terms of the process of reading, this led to a considerable product when it is followed correctly, that is to say, by the end of a successful reading process, readers are able to understand and read fluently by using the strategies of interpreting the express meaning of the text.

Weak Forms and Linking Words.

In English, as in all other languages, functional words do not have a dictionary definition, leaving aside words such as verbs, adjectives, and nouns. Content words are limited in number, including auxiliary verbs, pronouns, articles, conjunctions, and prepositions among others. Substantially, functional words has two types of pronunciation forms: a strong and a weak form. The strong form pronunciation (also called citation form/ full form) is stressed, and its pronunciation form is often found in the word's dictionary entry (Brown & Kondo-Brown, 2006). In the language function of linking words, English language has syllables, (Roach, 2009; Roach 2009b: syllable), and 'a consonant + vowel (CV)' sequence is the simplest and most universal syllable structure, which seems to be found in all languages. A syllable that follows the CV (consonant – vowel) and does not end in a consonant is known as *open syllable*, whereas a syllable that ends with a consonant is referred to as a *closed syllable*. Consequently, linking is the connection of the final sound of a word or syllable to the initial sound of the next (Celce-Murcia et al., 2010). It also occurs between 'vowels and vowels' (e.g., blue ink), 'consonants and vowels' (e.g., skip it), and 'consonants and consonants' (e.g., top person, hot cake) (Brown & Kondo-Brown, 2006).

As Brown and Kondo-Brown (2006) argues:

“One of the problems with connected speech as a discipline is that it is not a discipline or even a sub-discipline. Connected speech has interested some teachers and researchers over the past 30 years, but only a few people have

worked systematically on connected speech and those few have done so only sporadically. In the meantime, teachers continue to teach the phonemes of their language of focus and later wonder why their students' pronunciation is still inadequate, that is, why their students cannot put the phonemes together in anything approaching a native-like manner."

However, based on my teaching practice, students are truly aware of the importance of this aspect of connected speech while reading aloud.

Scripted role-play strategy.

The educational use of role-play has become more widespread in the EFL/ESL classroom. Harmer (2007) advocates the use of role-play for two reasons: because it is fun and motivating. He also points out its quieter students get the chance to express themselves in a more direct way, and the word of the classroom is broadened to include the outside world. According to Larsen-Freeman (2000), incorporating role-playing in the classroom makes a difference in the activities because it facilitates communication in the classroom. When the activities are taking place, teachers serve as an advisor, answering students' questions and observing their progress.

Most research on the use of role-play technique has been carried out. Suryani (2015) concluded the effectiveness of using role play in teaching speaking ability. The findings showed an improvement in the students' speaking performance since there was a significant score difference between the pre- test and post -test. Similarly, these results were confirmed in a study carried out by Krebt (2017) who examined how effective the use of role-play technique is on a group of Iraqi EFL college students when performing their speaking skills. It was determined that role play techniques provide an engaging learning environment for the students to flourish. In addition, such an environment leads to better attention to learning, and it engages them to participate in role-play techniques. In role-play techniques, students take a new identity and learn to use a foreign language for everyday interaction (Krebt, 2017).

Firstly, the ability to create a communicative environment in the classroom is one of the main teacher's main responsibilities since the teacher's role in role-playing learning is to teach students and explain the topic. Secondly, as teachers, we never know if students will be engaged in such activities, as it is reading aloud since reading is typically a self-indulgent activity that most students like doing in private. Others enjoy

reading, but they prefer not to do so at school precisely. Despite their lack of interest, some students are required to read aloud in front of their peers while also following instructions. Thirdly, role plays can help students to find emotional and academic connections with the text. It is assumed that teachers must have used role plays to consolidate new functional language, practice for a real-world activity, or prepare students for exams.

Krebt (2017) states that it is a great method to practice speaking in public and use new language. Even, drama teachers emphasize how acting, and dramatization helps learners in long-term memory retention of specific phrases, passages, events, and ideas. Considering the above, it can be inferred that the present action research supports student's oral production of connected speech in English by using reading scripted role-plays aloud.

Promoting this approach, researchers have been able to determine the efficiency of using scripted role-plays as a strategy in teaching. Idham et al (2022) conducted a study to explore the effect of role-playing techniques focused on the speaking skills of undergraduate students from Iraq. As it was previously mentioned, the authors also agree that recent education has been placed on student-centred education to ensure that EFL learners are able to master the four language skills. According to Wulandari et al (2021) the role-playing strategy for RA seems to be a very attractive activity for the students to use the script. In addition to this, the role-playing strategy for reading aloud may be divided into three categories: fully scripted, semi-scripted, and unscripted. The first category is the one where all the words are written in a fully scripted role-play. The authors also state that the main goal of a dialogue, after all, is to make each piece of a language meaningful and easy to remember (Idham et al., 2022). According to Livingstone (1983) in the semi-scripted role plays, there are missing words and students should know how to fill the gaps with the words that fit the situation. Likewise, Idham et al (2022) state these materials should be based on a real-life context for students. Moreover, this type of role-playing can be used with students at the upper beginner to intermediate level of English proficiency since they already know how to master more complex tasks since semi-scripted role-play is less structured and less controlled than fully scripted role-play.

Also, among the benefits of using role-play in the EFL classroom, the authors state:

- a) It helps students to build their confidence and inventiveness by motivating themselves to practice speaking activities.
- b) Students become proficient in English due to regular role-playing activities.
- c) It builds-up vocabulary for selecting appropriate words for each situation depending on the context.

Finally, authors were able to conclude that role play is an excellent strategy for developing student's speaking skills' competence.

Based on students' perceptions, another research examined the use of scripted role-play as a drama-focused method to encourage 7th graders' willingness to be part of speaking English. The results showed learners improved their speaking skills through role-play. Indeed, positive attitudes from their teachers provided them confidence to further develop their speaking skills. Therefore, in terms of perceptions towards the scripted role-play activities, a high percentage of students showed a positive attitude during their participation in the use of role-plays. (Lara Castro & Díaz Larenas, 2019)

3 Methodology

The present study corresponded to Action Research with a mixed method approach by combining and integrating qualitative and quantitative methods to collect data. According to Burns (2010) "Action research is part of a broad movement that has going on in education generally for some time. It is related to the ideas of 'reflective practice' and 'the teacher as a researcher' as it involves taking a self-reflective, critical, and systematic approach to exploring own teaching contexts described as a qualitative research method". Additionally, the use of mixed methods enables researchers to answer researcher questions with sufficient depth and breadth. On one hand, the quantitative approach helps a researcher to collect data from a large number of participants; this, increasing the findings to a wider population. On the other hand, the qualitative approach provides a deeper understanding of the problem being investigated. Both quantitative results can be triangulated with qualitative findings. The process of triangulation is the use of multiple data to develop a comprehensive understanding of a research problem (Carter et al., 2014).

Participants

It has been chosen a non-probabilistic sample composed of participants. The purposeful sample is composed by 30 students enrolled in 9th grade in an age range of 14 and 15 years old from a private school located in Chile. The group of freshmen in high school shares the same level of English, and these students were selected on the basis of the degree of EFL instruction considering they had started their formal English learning process when they were five years old in kindergarten. Particularly, these participants also were chosen because of the fact they presented difficulties in producing weak forms and did not make any linking when reading aloud in English. As their teacher, it was a concern since it used to lead to mispronunciations, above all their content knowledge in English; their enthusiasm to learn, and their motivation to participate in any challenge related to the English language components (speaking, listening, writing, reading comprehension, and culture).

Data collection

The action plan data of this study were gathered before, during and after the five-session intervention of 25 minutes long twice per week. These sessions were performed on site and conducted during the participant's regular schedule at school. Each session had a particular learning objective through the intervention development by dynamic activities and the use of two instruments for data collection. The following table describes how the session interventions was conducted.

Table 1

Stages of the AR

Session	Learning objective	Activities	Assessment	Data collection instrument
1	Assess students' initial level of production of linking words and weak forms	Video introduction to present a role-play.	Pre- Checklist students' initial level of production of linking words and weak forms	Checklist: Linking words and weak forms.
2	Demonstrate the ability to master a role-play.	Students are grouped in pairs to practice the conversation by choosing their role of the dialogue previously watched in the video.	A formative assessment: students read a scripted role-play aloud while performing and master a role-play.	Field notes
3	Present the strategy of connected speech: Linking words.	Review of consonant + vowel and vowel + vowel. Students are grouped in pairs to practice, produce and function connected speech by using the strategy of linking words.	Formative assessment: the students read a story aloud while practicing linking words sounds.	Field notes
4	Identify linking words on a scripted role- play.	Review of consonant + vowel and vowel + vowel. Students are grouped in pairs to practice, produce and function connected speech by using the strategy of linking words.	Formative assessment, students' reading aloud an interview and use of linking words while through identifying them and practicing it.	Field notes
5	Present the strategy of connected speech: Weak forms and identify its functions in English.	Review and practice the most common expressions by using weak forms on a scripted role-play.	Formative assessment: students read aloud on the list of the common expressions by using weak forms on a scripted role-play.	Field notes
6	Evaluate students' final oral production of linking words and weak forms in a scripted role-play. Assess participants' perceptions towards the use of linking words, weak forms and scripted role-play to support their oral production in English.	Performing a role-play by using weak forms on a scripted role-play.	Post-Checklist students' final level of production of linking words and weak forms. Focus group	Checklist: Linking words and weak forms. Focus group

Note: Own elaboration.

Data analysis

The data analysis in this study was followed by conceptual content analysis to determine the existence and frequency of concepts towards how supportive the use of scripted role-play on participants' oral production of Weak Forms and Linking Words was by reading a scripted role-play aloud. In regards the triangulation technique (Heigham & Croker, 2009) Different perspectives on a phenomenon were obtained by gathering data from different participants and using a variety of data collection methods like observations, interviews, and questionnaires. (p.11).

Instruments

The first instrument for data collection was a pre and a post checklist conducted to examine the level of features of connected speech on each student's oral production of linking words and weak forms when reading aloud scripted role-play most common expressions. For the purpose of facilitating the initial and final assessment, the teacher circled "yes" or "no" in response to the 10 out of 15 most common expressions found in dialogues, also adapted from Brown's pronunciation and phonetics': practical guide for teachers (Brown, 2014) on the section of connected speech. For instance, the first chart contained 10 words also elaborated for "Weaking Forms" while the second chart corresponded to "Linking Words" in response to 5 common expressions of said connected speech. The second instrument to collect data was field notes. These written records described students' oral production progress when linking and weak forms were practiced during the session's intervention. Field notes can be collected in a variety of formats, including written, dictated, and even through visual sketches (Phillippi & Lauderdale, 2018). Therefore, observations also known as field notes were registered with the aim of describing students' oral production progress when linking and weak forms were practised by reading aloud scripted role-play aloud, as it was a chance to remember not only student's behaviour, gestures, and moods but also other features of the classroom as a setting while the action research was conducted.

These data were triangulated with the third instrument, a focus group aimed to identify student's perceptions towards the use of scripted role-play as a support on student's oral production of connected speech in English of Weak Forms and Linking Words.

Kaehne and O'Connell (2010) point out that participants in focus groups should have an interest in the topic at hand, and they should be willing to participate constructively.

4 Results

The initial and final checklist

The initial and final checklist took place in the 9th graders' classroom, each participant came to the teacher's desk, and they read the 15 phrases aloud to examine their oral production on Weak Forms and Linking Words before and after the session's intervention.

Observations

With the aim of describe students' oral production progress when reading aloud Weak Forms and Linking Words found on the scripted role-plays handouts, descriptive field notes were used during the intervention. This instrument helped and developed over time; that is to say, field notes contained descriptive record as well as reflective information concerning specific observations. These notes were usually taken after monitoring each pair of participants while practicing reading scripted role-plays aloud. For instance, the observation table was certainly focused under the title of "Participants' oral production progress"; therefore, after each intervention these notes were written with its analysis, respectively.

Focus Group

A focus group was organized to identify students' perceptions towards the use of scripted role-play as a support on their oral production of Weak Forms and Linking Words. After the intervention, a number of 10 students were chosen randomly to respond and to be part of the discussion by answering 5 questions. It is important to mention that questions were elaborated and answered in Spanish since participants were more confident to speak their mother tongue instead of English Language; therefore, more data was provided in terms of their inner point of view towards the use of scripted role-play. During the focus group and along with the technology of using a voice-recorder was used to capture each participant's responses for subsequent transcription. Once audio recordings were transcribed, the next step was to find key information to identify students' perceptions towards said support.

5 Discussion

The discussion will be presented in one category according to one of the specific objectives of this action research study, which is as follows, to identify students' perceptions towards the use of scripted role-play to support their oral production of linking and weak forms. The quantitative data was analysed to measure improvement in participants' oral production. A paired *t*-test method was used to test the mean difference between the Pre and Post checklist based on the percentage of success of each student. The difference between these two variables for the same group of participants were triangulated with a focus group to identify students' perceptions of said support. The interventions showed to be significant as participants achieved improvement in their speaking skills from a 38% to a 76% respectively as well as reading aloud in English (Figure 1).

Figure 1

Note: Paired *t*- Test contrast between the percentage of Success by Phrase from the Pre and Post Checklist.

Figure 2

Note: Graph bar Success by phrases

Considering the aim of this action research, seven subthemes emerged from the five questions discussed on the focus group, as it is presented in Figure 3.

Figure 3

Note: Conceptual map from the Focus Group

Subthemes 1- 2: Foreign Language Anxiety/ Confidence

In reviewing the literature, Chapman (2022) states some students, especially beginners are reluctant readers, and they do not want to read aloud because they feel embarrassed; they do not like attention focused on them because they are not confident in their reading. Very little was found in the literature on the association between the emotions and attitude towards how a non-native English speaker deals with speaking a foreign language in front of their peers. However, participants did a remarkable emphasis on their speaking fluency since it dramatically changed after the interventions were developed as they feel more confident when it comes to reading English aloud and also able to interact with others without feeling awkward in case there were words misspelled or mispronounced. Participants were asked to share their perceptions of their feelings about speaking English before intervention started. Students were able to overcome the feelings of fear, worry, and nervousness when it comes to speaking English. It can be also noticed in the students' answers that participants feel a certain spirit of satisfaction when they expressed their "fear" as a situation that used to happen in the past.

- S1: *"A mí me daba miedo que alguien dijera que no pronunciaba bien inglés y eso como que me daba vergüenza" (FGD1).*

- S4: *"Tenía miedo de leer en voz alta en las clases inglés porque temía hacerlo mal" (FGD1).*

- S6: *"Antes de las intervenciones igual sentía mi inglés al hablarlo en voz alta, no era tan fluido" (FGD1).*

Improving the skill of confidence was not the aim of this study; however, participants pointed out their perceptions towards the strategies and methodologies of teaching used during the intervention as a positive instance of being exposed to the language and speaking English with their peers. Actually, once students were able to understand and identify the main fear, their confidence in speaking English changed considerably due to practise and repetition was part of the essence of this action research.

- S1: *"Me siento mucho más segura cuando me piden leer párrafos o bien textos en la clases de inglés" (FGD1),*

- S4: *“Siento que la etapa de la inseguridad de leer en voz alta y de las dificultades en la pronunciación, ya está superada” (FGD1),*
- S7: *“Ahora siento más seguridad” (FGD1),* - S8: *“Entiendo mejor y esto me ha generado más confianza al participar en clases” (FGD1),*
- S9: *“Me hizo sentir más confianza en mí misma” (FGD1).*

Subthemes 3-4: Self-awareness/ Oral production improvement

Participants mentioned and agreed that the use of this strategy helped them not only to communicate effectively with their peers but also to improve their pronunciation. They also added that learning both strategies of connected speech in English by reading scripted role-play aloud helped to understand syllable sounds and connections between words through a dynamic and attractive technique of practising English naturally instead feeling pressure of being assessed. The Chilean National Curriculum of Education states reading aloud is essential for students since activities and practice not only help students to foster reading ability and basic skill but also it helps to improve oral expression and to support oral production skills. It is important to bear in mind the possible bias in these responses, because in accordance with the main difference between the “before” and “after” the intervention in students’ oral production and speaking skills’ competence, they referred as it was great personal progress on the domain of reading English aloud since their confidence was truly consolidated due to the awareness and knowledge in both strategies learnt.

- S2: *“Ahora al tratar de expresarme en inglés, sé cómo se pronuncian ciertas palabras o cómo iría la unión entre dos palabras para hacer que suene más fluido” (FGD1),*
- S6: *“Siento que mi lectura en voz alta ha mejorado, y aunque quizás mi inglés no sea perfecto en la pronunciación, sé diferenciar cuando tengo que hacer linking o weak en las palabras, o sea, sé cuándo hacerlo y cuando no” (FGD1),*
- S8: *“Hay palabras que no se escriben como se pronuncian y también depende del acento porque lo que más se recalca normalmente es el inglés estadounidense y el inglés británico que son bastante diferentes, entonces estas estrategias de linking words and weak forms, se pueden aplicar a todas las palabras, son como reglas que se aplican a todas las palabras, entonces*

no es como que uno se tenga que aprender las palabras en específico porque con saberse la regla la puede aplicar a todo el vocabulario” (FGD1).

Particularly, both strategies of connected speech (weaking and linking) supported their pronunciation in English because they have already studied when it is precise to link certain expressions when it comes to read aloud, provoking a self-consciousness of their English-speaking skills as well as identifying the difference between the British accent and American accent. Despite their perceptions related to their English proficiency; they were honest to state being able to communicate without hesitation since intervention was brought into the classroom.

- S4: *“O sea yo no hablo un inglés perfecto, pero por ejemplo ahora si digo palabras de corrido porque por lo general antes de conocer linking words, yo me frenaba en las palabras, entonces ahora las puedo decir de corrido y eso siento que suena mejor que andarse pausando a cada rato” (FGD1),*

- S5: *“Yo también he notado diferencias, en la confianza y en la fluidez por así decirlo porque gracias a esto he aprendido a leer más fluido, es decir, aprendiendo esto uno lee más fluido” (FGD1),*

-S6: *“Siento que tengo una lectura más fluida y un habla también más fluida y eso como que me hace como más segura al momento de hablar y como a sentirme capaz de poder hacerlo” (FGD1),*

- S8: *“Pues confirmando lo que han mencionado mis compañeros, se nota que hay una diferencia en mi pronunciación y al leer principalmente” (FGD1).*

Subthemes 5-6-7: Innovative Teaching Methods/ Student’s Learning Outcomes/ Collaborative Learning.

Consistent with the literature, this action research found that participants reported feeling more confident whether for practicing as well as for asking for support to produce connected speech and/or language functions of linking words among their peers. Also, participants added that the aim of speaking as naturally as native speakers and the extensive work with weak and strong forms may facilitate their perception in a natural speech in front of a daily life context as it was during the practice of reading scripted role-plays aloud. These three sub-themes were grouped since the

findings were unexpected and suggest that combining these three elements in the classroom is essential to achieve the aim of the present study. These results reflect those of Mangaleswaran and Aziz (2019) who also found that using CLT encourages teachers to provide a chance to the students to express and exchange their ideas in English.

- S1: *“¿Si me gustó aprender?, pues sí, principalmente porque por un lado yo lo encontraba necesario aprenderlo y usted lo enseñó de una manera bastante divertida especialmente con los juegos de roles, lo llamativo de las presentaciones, daban ganas de estudiárselo y aprendérselo para mejorar así la pronunciación y la lectura” (FGD1),*

- S3: *“A mí me gustó sobre todo porque fue una forma distinta para aprender porque es más fácil en cierta forma, y que nos integrara estos conocimientos de forma extra a las clases normales, se me hizo mucho más fácil aprender” (FGD1),*

- S4: *“A mí me gustó porque fue entretenido y dinámico y esto ayuda mucho para un futuro y especialmente si es inglés porque abre puertas al mundo y esto mejora lo que es la pronunciación, la conexión de las palabras y que suelen ser difíciles porque no todos saben inglés, entonces esto facilita y lo hace más entretenido, estuvo muy bueno aprender la estrategia de linking y weaking” (FGD1),*

- S6: *“A mí me más que nada me facilitó por la manera en que nos enseñó usted con los juegos de roles y todo eso más que por regirse a una clase clásica por así decirlo, más dinámico y variado, eso me facilitó mucho el aprendizaje” (FGD1),*

- S10: *“Esta actividad es bastante atractiva y dinámica y una entretenida forma de enseñarnos inglés” (FGD1).*

Students' comments indicated that teaching strategies used were innovative, dynamic, and attractive ones. By the time it came to introduce this new practice inside the classroom, I faced it as a challenge, however; once the motivation was achieved by using communicative-oriented approaches, students were able to improve speaking skills, competences as important as knowledge in English as a subject and from my side to strength and improve my own teaching methods.

- S1: *“En el caso de los juegos de roles, yo lo encontré como algo práctico debido a que en sí son muchas cosas de la vida diaria, situaciones de la vida diaria en las cuales uno ocupa esas palabras usualmente; por ejemplo, ‘Estar en la casa de un amigo’ y una puede ocupar esas palabras clave como usted nos dice y pronunciaciones clave para ese tipo de palabras. Y en sí siento que mejoró mi expresión oral precisamente, el tener un vocabulario más amplio y tener las respectivas pronunciaciones de cada uno y poder expresarse mejor”* (FGD1),

- S2: *“Al aprender ambas estrategias pude notar grandes avances a nivel personal y en sí aprender algo nuevo en especial la parte de idiomas ya que siempre me ha llamado más la atención”* (FGD1),

- S3: *“Linking words lo entendí más que nada como que si hay una frase, no hacer tantas pausas, entonces así se lee de corrido, y en el weaking forms era más que nada la pronunciación por ejemplo yo lo he visto en las películas o en las canciones que no marcan mucho y hay gente que las omite (sounds)”* (FGD1),

- S6: *“Me ayudó a comprenderlo más, además de lo que han dicho mis compañeros que les ayudó a la pronunciación, a la seguridad al hablar y a la fluidez”* (FGD1),

- S9: *“Me gustó la simpleza de esta técnica ya que pude lograr otros grandes avances en muy poco tiempo y una mejora notable tanto para pronunciar como para escuchar a una persona nativa del habla inglesa (FGD1),*

- S10: *“Más que cambiar mi pronunciación o darme más confianza, me enseñó que el inglés tiene un mayor trasfondo. Yo antes no sabía que hay palabras que se pueden conectar, con las estrategias que nos enseñó se me hizo más fácil; primero entender esta nueva mecánica y también me ayudó a entender que el inglés no es tan sólo leer, sino que tiene algunas características o reglas que te van a ayudar a entenderlo y a hablarlo mejor”* (FGD1).

Based on participants' perceptions towards the use of scripted role-play to support their oral production in English, it can be stated that learners have reliably demonstrated an improvement and learning upon the completion of the intervention. Also, participants are able to identify the use of both strategies taught in different contexts; for instance, songs, movies, and celebrities who are English Native speakers. Furthermore, students mentioned their pronunciation changed positively after the intervention as a remarkable experience from this action research.

- S5: *"La actividad de juego de roles me sirvió mucho para poder practicar el inglés, es más fluido y en tiempo real con mis compañeros, siento que al hacer eso es un trabajo mutuo porque si uno no sabe la palabra, nos ayudamos entre sí, y se produce ayuda colectiva"* (FGD1),

- S3: *"Yo creo que fue una súper buena idea porque en el futuro quizás si uno se va a otro país, uno debe mantener un diálogo con personas y más encima si uno hace esto con otros compañeros, ellos nos corrigieron en case de cualquier error, como lo que me pasó a mí en ciertas ocasiones"* (FGD1),

-S6: *"La actividad de juego de roles al ser interactiva como que mejoró la comprensión, y al realizarla con nuestros compañeros, tenemos más confianza, nos pudimos ayudar y sentir más la actividad y mejora en todo"* (FGD1),

- S8: *"Me gustó trabajar de esa forma haciendo las actividades en conjunto"* (FGD1),

- S10: *"Se hace más dinámico ir aprendiendo al mismo tiempo que el otro porque hay una gran habilidad que es estar trabajando con un compañero y que los dos tengan el mismo nivel de inglés para ir aprendiendo juntos y enseñando cosas al otro si alguno no sabe, entonces es una forma bastante didáctica y se pasa bien"* (FGD1),

- S9: *"Aparte de ser entretenido, esto de la expresión oral fue compartida, eso significa que la conversación en inglés puede ser mucho más fluida y ayuda a entender a otra persona que también habla inglés y así esto sirve en un futuro"* (FGD1).

Participants shared their perceptions based on how efficient the development of activities as teamwork was. Working in pairs was meaningful for them as they understood the use of role-plays as an interactive strategy to be done inside the classroom. They reflected as they helped each other to reach their goal of producing weak forms or linking words when they were practising them. This is due to students sharing their knowledge with their peers as they were respectful and empathetic when it came to supporting their classmates' pronunciation by giving and receiving feedback.

6 Conclusion

The issue that was addressed in this action research was the communicative skills of a group of students from a private school in Chile. The speaking skills competence domain that English lessons had in the 9th graders was affected by the lack of self-confidence in speaking English in front of their peers or the self-awareness for mispronounce certain words. This can be supported by comments such "I was scared at speaking English", made by the majority of participants of this study when asked about their own perceptions from reading aloud in English. Consequently, as a supportive solution for the previous issue, this action research aimed at exploring the use of scripted role-plays in English to support the ability to produce connected speech in English when reading aloud. Thus, the contents of said scripted role-plays were elaborated to practise and master connecting words and phrases in English. Important as it might seem to the use of scripted role-plays to support EFL learners' oral production of linking words and weak forms when reading aloud it can be concluded that this study has found that generally the matter of implementing features of connected speech in English in lessons can be as attractive as productive in EFL and ESL learners. Particularly, this study found that participants struggled with foreign language anxiety, due to the fear of public speaking, their self-confidence in hand by their self-awareness, specifically when they were not known of how to pronounce certain words in English. However, once the intervention concluded, participants were able to notice that their oral production of English significantly improved. In addition, the group of 9th graders sheds light on the innovative teaching methods implemented during the sessions and how their learning outcomes were consolidated.

Although the current study is based on a small sample of participants, the findings suggest the insights gained may have important implications for teachers willing to implement innovative teaching strategies by using dynamic activities to expose students to the language of English. Also, it is highly regarded that well-distributed group work encouraged in the classroom, for this allows learners to work collaboratively within their peers as well as developing social skills, which aspects of spoken delivery result in communicating meaningfully in class. In addition, further research in this field would be of great help in EFL and ESL students' oral production of English when reading aloud; materials and instruments used in this action research can be adjusted into any school context, university context and/or any group of EFL and ESL learners.

How can the use of scripted role-plays support 9th graders' connected speech when reading aloud in English? The reading aloud scripted role-plays supported the connected speech in English to the group of freshmen students in high school from a private school in Chile. It was not only a support to read fluently but also, students were precise and certain of feeling more comfortable and confident when it comes to reading in front of an audience. In addition, the group of teenagers mentioned that the most meaningful moments were when they came practising in pairs because they were able to feed back to each other if they produced mispronounced words in English. The action research was a success in terms of how effective this strategy was in the group of 30 students.

In terms of connected speech, the group of 9th graders was very interested in the theory behind phonology and phonetics in English; these in hand by the role play strategy students agreed that all the contexts were fruitful in terms that they can face those scenarios in the future, and they already know how to interact with English speakers. In addition, this action research study has a number of important implications for future practice, as well as for updating the current Chilean Curriculum of Education in the matter of teaching English as a subject in the Chilean classrooms with the pursuit of meaningful learning in our students.

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